

Urb: urban sound analysis and storage project

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces Urb, a system for automated analysis and storing of an urban soundscape. Urb complements traditional sound maps, allowing the direct access of its features at any arbitrary moment since the system's boot, thus facilitating the study of the soundscape's evolution and the differences between specific timeframes, and facilitating artistic approaches to such data. In this paper, we will describe the creative and technical aspects considered during its early development, whilst addressing its three fundamental parts: the hardware and software for capturing and transmitting audio recordings, the software for analyzing the soundscape and the management of the database.

Keywords: Sound Scape, sound analysis, Networked Music, Timeline; Database.

1. INTRODUCTION

The youth has been completely conquered by this electronic world that is acoustic, intuitive, "holistic", this is, global and total, a new world that put in the shelve the old scientific world with its quantities, its immensities, our "First World" super-industrialized. The youth prefers the Third World because he is still acoustic and oral, and invites to total immersion (...)[1]. According to McLuhan's critical thought, the 60's and 70's electronic revolution marked the return of the ear as a sovereign organ for cultural human perception. This socio-cultural transformation underlined the Western man's necessity of constant absorption. It is within this frame that the soundscape studies become more systematic and its presence as an artistic tool more persistent. This was not a new subject, but rather a new one that found fresh stable grounds within the constant multidirectional cultural and ecologic awareness that dictates the Electronic Era.

The notion of soundscape is increasingly relevant not only in contemporary culture and acoustic ecology, but also in many other fields, such as artistic productions.

The soundscape concept and movement were presented to us and based on Schafer's considerations of environment studies in the early 70's [2]. According to Iges, Murray Schafer's utopia, with some similarities of Pierre Schaeffer's analyses about the sound, it would be

to impose some kind of order in the sound environment with the aim of achieving a "sound ecology"[3].

With the development of studies and sound collections, near the turn of the century, is made aware that the soundscape depends on the listeners' understanding and interpretation of a soundscape[4]. With sound files so freely available, like freesound project¹, and portable memory-based recorders so inexpensive, sound maps have become increasingly common on the Internet. Usually the sound maps are based on a Google-style map that is used to situate the geographic origin of the recordings, e.g. World Listening Project². *However, lacking any coherent temporal perspective, and usually lacking any interpretative analysis, the listener is left trying to imagine what has been recorded and what significance it has.*[5]. An interesting variant of this approach is a live microphone in a fixed location that is constantly streaming audio like the Locustream Sound Map developed³ [6].

Given the project relevance, in partnership with artists and research center interested in networked music and sonic performance, is developed as one of the important parts in the recent created NMSAT (Networked Music & Soundart Timeline) to support important collaborations in this area as Eu-phonix (with SARC Belfast, CRiSAP LCC University of the Arts London, CultureLab University of Newcastle, LORNA Reykjavik, KIBLA Malibor, Le Hangar Barcelona, STEIM Amsterdam), Audio Ambiances (LAMES CNRS Universite' de Provence, CRESSON CNRS E' cole d'Architecture de Grenoble, ENST/Telecom Paristech/Eurocom Sophia-Antipolis/EHESS), TransatLab puf— Franco-American academic partnership (School of the Art Institute of Chicago SAIC), Locustream (in collaboration with communities of field recordists and phonographers such as WLP—World Listening Project)[7].

To support the project, they developed an autonomous «LocustreamBox» - a small computer dedicated to task of streaming audio and configured to connect automatically to their server and related systems such as online interfaces or setups for installations[8].

The Locustream sound map has a very interesting approach to the soundscape but still has the time problem. It is very hard to have a good description if you cannot compare with different moments of the past. So,

¹ www.freesound.org

² www.worldlisteningproject.org

³ http://locusonus.org/soundmap/034/)by de Locus Sonus project

combining the problem of temporal coherence presented by most of the Sound Maps with conceptual and physical path shown by Locus Sonus, we started to develop a plan to work a complementary access to a sound map that is discrete in time.

2. PROPOSAL

Urb claim to be a complement to the approach of the sound environment study, presenting a proposal for a system based on available and cheap hardware and open source software. Thus, it may be a tool with a very large ramp of development and flexibility to be used, not only by environmentalists and urban planners, but also by artists with creative intentions.

The implementation of the project is divided into 3 phases:

1st: design, prototyping and development of a listening point and database;

2nd: Create 4 listening points in the city of Porto; develop tools to access the database; invite artists from different areas to develop work with the data in real time and non real-time.

3rd: Make the site, database and the software public; make integration with Project Locustream Sound map; present approaches to data processing systems for artistic purposes; encourage spontaneous initiative for the multiplication of listening points.

3. HARDWARE

3.1 Raspberry Pi

The first approach to the microcomputer choice was analyzing the Locustream Box. They used a PC Engines 500 MHz AMD Geode LX800 using Gentoo Linux distribution[9].

This hardware was sufficient for what we need. The problem is that it would be needed to order the different parts and put them together, plus the total cost is around 150€. For us this seemed to be a major problem to a project that wants to grow spontaneously under the individual motivation. The Raspberry Pi is a credit-card-sized single-board computer developed in the UK by the Raspberry Pi Foundation with the intention of promoting the teaching of basic computer science in schools. It has an ARM1176JZF-S 700 MHz processor VideoCore IV GPU, and 512 megabytes of RAM. It does not include a built-in hard disk or solid-state drive, but uses an SD card for booting and long-term storage.[10]

The Raspberry Pi presents a solution for most of our needs. It is quite cheap, it is already built, and it has a very enthusiastic community working to develop the hardware and system. Most of them, around the Pure Data⁴ on Rasperry, a fundamental tool for our project.

3.2 USB ADC

The Raspberry PI does not have an analogic input, so it is necessary a USB sound card. Not all the USB Analog

to Digital Converters work with the Raspberry Pi and it's important to slow down the speed device to 1.1 adding

```
$>> dwc_otg.speed=1
```

to the string in the file /boot/cmdline.txt [11].

As we are only using the computer as a listening point, we change the USB ADC to default changing the /etc/modprobe.d/alsa-base.conf file replacing the

```
$>> options snd-usb-audio index=-2
```

string to

```
$>> options snd_bcm2835=-2
```

and creating a /.libao in the home directory with

```
$>> driver=alsa
$>> dev=default
```

strings.

3.3 Electret Microphone

This is a critical point, because it is very complicated to found a microphone that resists to the weather conditions and with an enough small size to put in places like windows or breathers and not expensive enough to be in a public place. We decide to use the Peter Sinclair suggestion for the Locus Sonus Project with a DIY microphone, Figure1, that only needs 5v power (perfect for the USB connections) using a electret microphone.[12]

Figure 1. The Locus Mic DIY circuit.

4. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE DESCRIPTION

4.1 Sending and Storing Data

When sending and storing data on-line, Urb relies on Python and MySQL to preform the tasks. The Python module works as an outside agent, responsible for building a query out of a float package put together by Pure Data, and sending it to a MySQL database. This second component introduces a concurrent programming paradigm⁵ into Urb's software architecture, as Python

⁴ <http://puredata.info/>

⁵ "A concurrent application will have two or more threads in progress at some time. This can mean that the application has two threads that are being swapped in and out by the operating system on a single core

and Pd are seemingly working simultaneously through unidirectional message passing communication, via [shell] object. The presence of a second programming language on the client side of the system is deeply connected to the aesthetic and functional aspirations of the project. While it is advisable to keep a clean architecture and, therefore, avoid the presence of additional languages, the presented solutions for a Pd based project led to the decision of using a second language as a mean of keeping the project intentions intact facing technical distortion.

As a programming environment focused on media and artistic production, Pure Data relies on community developed externals and libraries in order to perform SQL connections. At the moment, communication between Pd and SQLite or PostgreSQL databases are ensured by some externals⁶, which is still a far from optimal set of solutions when, like in Urb, as we will explain, using MySQL as a relational database management system is a binding need.

Although PostgreSQL presents itself as the most advanced open-source database system available⁷, its usage implies the necessity of a dedicated server⁸; a service that exceeds the dimensions of an embryonic project like Urb. On the other hand, SQLite lacks the user and permissions management needed⁹ to build a much-needed community around this project. As was underlined before, Urb's aesthetic agenda comprises easy access to the database in order to progressively build a clear picture of the city's soundscape and promote a consistent usage of that material within the composition scope. Therefore, between PostgreSQL's over complexity and SQLite's deficiency on social tools, MySQL turns out to be the fittest solution to Urb's data storage necessities, being a system that guarantees the possibility of social management with a simple shared server hosting service. Also, MySQL is a quite popular database system, which in the long term implies a much more rapid and responsive community, and a rather extensive collection

processor. These threads will be "in progress"—each in the midst of its execution—at the same time." [21]

⁶ Listed on Pd's official website are two different collections of externals whose purpose is to provide connection to a variety of relational databases. SQL library has no external to connect to a MySQL database and psql is reserved to PostgreSQL [22]

⁷ "PostgreSQL is the hammer of the database world (...) It has plug-ins for natural-language parsing, multidimensional indexing, geographic queries, custom datatypes, and much more. It has sophisticated transaction handling, has built-in stored procedures for a dozen languages, and runs on a variety of platforms." [23]

⁸ Right now, Urb is being hosted at a Hostgator's shared server. According to Hostgator's services PostgreSQL is only available for Dedicated and VPS servers upon request. <https://support.hostgator.com/articles/specialized-help/postgresql>

⁹ "An SQLite database has no authentication or authorization data. Instead, SQLite depends on file system permissions to control access to the raw database file. This essentially limits access to one of three states: complete read/write access, read-only access, or no access at all. Write access is absolute, and allows both data modification and the ability to alter the structure of the database itself." [24]

of web articles and forum threads, both positive attributes for a development tool.

With MySQL laid down as a vital option for the project, Pure Data's insufficiencies towards this database system needed to be overthrown. Without any available externals and with C's development time being drawback to the challenge of writing some new ones, the usage of additional languages became a viable hypothesis. Within Max, connecting to a MySQL database is a process that needs the support of Java. Queries are sent through Nick Rothwell's MySQL Java class¹⁰ loaded into the [mxj] object; an approach easily ported to Pd through its [pdj] object, whose API is based on the [mxj] implementation¹¹, making classes transferable between the two environments. So within Max, Java works as an interpreted language just like his host, using Java Virtual Machine as an interpreter for the loaded code¹². Every time a message passes through the [pdj] inlet an access to the JVM is taking place, which can turn out to be minor step back in terms of performance, even though in this specific case, the message being passed is a list containing all the needed values.

In addition, and most importantly, by using these objects, one is importing into the patch the connection time needed for the code to access the on-line database with its query. So, this means that Pd would be responsible for handling both analysis and connection, being the second an obstacle to the first. Although this freezing time represents no significant disadvantage for a patch with a sampling rate of 5'', the same cannot be said to a patch with a dynamic sampling rate, responsive to significant audio events captured at the input.

With C representing an unnecessary amount of time in development and Java a blockage within the patch, Python revealed himself as a reasonable solution. Python is a high-level easy to learn multi-purpose language that is historically known for its harmonious cooperation with Linux and MySQL, a fact that in part led to the formation of the LAMP software bundle¹³. One can argue that Java's inclusion in the system through the [pdj] object is not mandatory. OSC could easily serve the purpose without damaging the performance of the patch. However, when developing for Raspberry Pi, not only Python is officially the primary programming language

¹⁰ net.loadbang.sql.mxj.MySQL
http://www.maxobjects.com/?v=objects&id_obj=3571&PHPSESSID=09ef5816e5d955699b350dedd401d647

¹¹ "PDJ enables you to write java code to interact with pure-data objects. The API is totally based on Cycling74 Max/MSP 'mxj' object implementation. This will enable java mxj objects to run on pure-data with pdj." [25]

¹² "The class files that live in the classes folder are what are known as byte code files. Unlike C externals, which are compiled into platform-specific machine code, Java byte code can be executed on any system that will run the JVM (Java Virtual Machine)." Max6/java-doc/tutorial

¹³ "MySQL is the dominant open source database management system: it is being used increasingly to build very significant applications based on the LAMP (Linux-Apache-MySQL-PHP/Perl/Python)(...)" [26]

for the hardware¹⁴, but also, interpreter and packages are available by default on both Debian and Gentoo distributions[13]. The readiness of Python when compared to the strict hardware and software specifications to make Java to compile builds a scenario where Python outstands as a much more robust and pragmatic solution than Java. [14]

Python's easy and flexible syntax allied to a stable MySQL library, MySQLdb, result on a fast implementation of a straight-forward yet effective script to send queries to a MySQL database that is easily accessible through the shell thanks to the language's script mode. Assuming that Urb's python script is in the /home/pi directory, the following command sends the appended list of 12 floats, one for each audio feature, to the MySQL database.

```
$>> python home/pi/urbsql.py 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0
0 0 0 0 0
```

When run from Pd, the command can be constructed with a combination of [pack], [list] and [prepend] objects resulting on a string that is ready to be passed through the [shell] object, figure2.

Figure2. Construction of the shell command on a Pd patch.

4.2 The Database

At the moment, since Urb is still on a prototype phase, the amount of data being produced and stored is minimal and as so, database management is yet to become a challenge. It is well established for now that each location, each sound recollection point will have its own table on the database, being that each table will take the name of its actual urban location, figure3.

The structure of each table is rather simple. Thirteen columns, one for each audio feature plus a first row that is using Unix Timestamp as a mean of identification and time localization of the event described in the row. The continuous nature of the timestamp provides not only a stable sequence to order entries but also enclosures meaningful information in itself by tagging the exact moment of the event and allowing further readings by

crossing data from other sources. For the exception of the first column that takes integers with a display width of 11, all the other columns store varchar data width a display width of 255.

#	Coluna	Tipo	Agrupamento (Collation)	Atributos	Nulo	Omissão	Extra
1	Id	int(11)			Não	None	AUTO_INCREMENT
2	pitch	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
3	amp	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
4	brightness	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
5	centroid	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
6	flatness	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
7	flux	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
8	kurtosis	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
9	rolloff	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
10	skewness	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
11	spread	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
12	zerocrossing	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	
13	Irregularity	varchar(255)	utf8_unicode_ci		Não	None	

Figure3. Structure of a generic Urb MySQL table

Along side with Urb's database, a series of data visualization and retrieval tools are being designed in order to keep the dialogue sustainable even for the non-technical user. It is of the most importance that Urb's data remains relevant and useable for the musician, composer or citizen without computational expertise, furthermore, all records are intended to be cleared of any composition methodology. The handling of Urb's data does not mean to be programmatically defined in any way.

Already implemented are two different PHP scripts that play a small part on what is expected to be a stable and refined project of data visualization and retrieval. For now, these two scripts are responsible for the following outputs:

- Displaying the data of a specific table as an HTML table. Regarded as a production tool, this allows monitoring the data flux without needing to log in to the host control panel.

- Export the data of a specific table as a .csv file. Due to safety constraints, the direct accesses to the contents of a MySQL database are often not possible. This is the case with Javascript and other JS based languages and frameworks like ProcessingJS. The way to avoid this technical predicament is to build a server side script that queries the database and exports the result as text file. Urb's actual script exports all the data on a database; each call o to the PHP script downloads the .csv file with the most recent set of data, making it accessible through Javascript.

Multiple users and restrictions strategies are yet to be defined and such decisions will be taken according to what the project itself dictates as more appropriate. Software architectural foundations have been set in a way that the gathering and distributing functions of the system work fluently and in a robust way, keeping options open as how exactly accesses will be managed in the future. For now, the main intention is to keep Urb as an inviting platform for the users of the so-called creative programming frameworks such as Max/MSP, Pure Data, Processing, ProcessingJS, openFrameworks, Cinder, Nodebox, Shoebot, among others.[15] With the already implemented code, Urb has reached a maturity state that guarantees a fast and thorough development and

¹⁴ "Does it have an official programming language? By default, we will be supporting Python as the educational language. Any language which will compile for ARMv6 can be used with the Raspberry Pi, though; so you are not limited to using Python." [10]

evolution of the project into a ready-to-use tool and sharp investigation document.

5. SOUND ANALYSIS AND INFORMATION FOR THE DATA BASE

All the sound analysis is made on the Pure Data patch.

The first part of the patch is about the audio input. It is for adjusting the level, figure 4, and to equalize the sound in case that you have some problems with noise, as from a vent or electricity, figure 5.

Figure 4. pd input

Figure 5. pd equalizer

The second part is where the analysis happens. The patch analyzes 12 different elements or descriptors of the sound. The first two are *Pitch* and *Amplitude*.

Pitch: using the native Pd-extended object *sigmund~*.

Sigmund~ analyzes an incoming sound into sinusoidal components, which may be reported individually or combined to form a pitch estimate.¹⁵

Amplitude: using another native object *avg~* that computes the mean amplitude of its input signal since it last received a bang. The mean amplitude is the sum of the absolute values of the input divided by the number of samples received.¹⁶

The other 10 features are from the *timbreID*¹⁷.

timbreID is a Pd external collection developed by William Brent. It is composed of a group of objects for extracting timbral features, and a classification object that manages the resulting database of information. The objects are designed to be easy to use and adaptable for a number of purposes.^[16]

It implements a collection of low-level spectral audio descriptors, such as:

Centroid is defined as the center of gravity of the magnitude spectrum,

Kurtosis gives a measure of the flatness of a distribution around its mean value,

Flatness is the ratio of the geometric mean of magnitude spectrum to the arithmetic mean of magnitude spectrum. A very noisy spectrum without clear shape should have a high flatness value,

Flux is defined as the squared difference between the normalized magnitudes of successive spectral distributions,

Irregularity is the comparison of how much each frequency bin compares to its immediate neighbors. A jagged spectrum, irregularity will be high, and for smooth contoured spectra, it will be low,

Mfcc represents the shape of the spectrum with few coefficients,

Roll-off is a measure of spectral shape, which is used to distinguish between voiced and unvoiced speech.

Skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of a distribution around its mean value,

Spread is the spread of the spectrum around mean value,

Zero-crossing rate is the number of times the signal cross the zero axe. [16][17][18]

The reasons that we are using are *timbreID* are: the Open Source nature, is very robust and stable, and was already tested and validated in other projects like *earGram*[19].

Such complete timbral features increase the project ability to respond to future demands or needs leaving the project scope flexible to ecological or artistic exploration and investigation.

Every five minutes the patch calculates the main value of each feature of that time and sends that value for the database, figure 6. During our tests we realize that the five minutes window is a sustainable amount of time to provide a clear “image” of the urban soundscape in a larger scale of time. It is a manageable number of entries to the database and doable to its storage in a long-term situation. It is around 553MB for a century of information for each listening point.

Figure 6. pd descriptors

As a future work we are studying a possible interest in developing an intelligent window that changes its duration, according the sound characteristics.

This descriptors data is a very powerful information. In the last years, the research about sound classification and genre identification is increasing exponentially. With the classification and similarity tools, Urb, in very near

¹⁵ sigmund~ object's help patch

¹⁶ avg~ object's help patch

¹⁷ <http://williambrent.conflations.com/pages/research.html>.

future, can give detail information about every 5 minutes of a soundscape, not only quantitative information but also especially qualitative information. Saying if the sound is more industrial or natural, speech or non-speech, noisy or pitched, and compare with other moments or with other soundscapes.

This is not only an ecological and social tool but also an artistic tool. The classification tools are already used in concatenative sound synthesis[19][16][20] for example, and with Urb this process can be controlled by a sound scape. Eco-Structuralism¹⁸ already uses sound and ecological structures to apply in music creation, and with Urb you have a repository of eco structures from soundscapes that you can use to music or visual creation.

The final patch part is the connection to the database previously described in section 4.

6. FUTURE WORK AND PERSPECTIVES

The first tests to assess the resistance of the hardware have shown a very positive outlook about the data sent to the database. With about 24 hours of analysis, and even with a brief look, it was easy to draw some conclusions, as the peak times of loudness (8:13 – 8:23) or silence (4:53 – 5:03) during that day,

Year	month	day	hour	min	amp
2012	12	13	4	53	0.228982;
2012	12	13	4	58	1.114694;
2012	12	13	5	3	3.069494;
(...)					
2012	12	13	8	13	48.119511;
2012	12	13	8	18	50.113361;
2012	12	13	8	23	46.514568;

or that the rain around 20:00 increases spectrum's frequency center and size.

Year	month	day	hour	min	centroid	spread
2012	12	12	20	18	1432	2.104941;
2012	12	12	20	23	1487	2.042615;
2012	12	12	20	28	1398	2.102901;
(...)						
2012	12	13	4	43	1218	1.732905;
2012	12	13	4	48	1167	1.8436;

With the system working it will be possible to develop and link to tools that use the maximum capacity in having such detailed descriptors of sound. And thus, we have access to accurate sound characteristics of a particular location, not only during a certain time window, but also since the Urb's boot.

It will be possible to access to the database, not only through a temporal index, but also through some sound characteristics. For example, moments that the sound exceeded certain intensity, number of times that the sound had a more clear pitch, situations mainly constituted by the sound of voices, ...

Using the data will serve to feed an adaptable viewer where you can graphically assess the soundscape evolution.

¹⁸ Eco-structuralism is a new approach to music composition designed to maintain the characteristics and context of a sound whilst not necessarily using the original recording data directly. [27]

Anyway, the project is very focused on developing research and finding ways on how this data can be used in a creative and artistic process and we will spend great part of our efforts in this area of the investigation. Some experiments in this field are already ongoing and we are simultaneously interact with artistic communities that work with sonorization, visualization and composition from data to systematize approaches to this material and create or adapt tools to facilitate this process. Although the results are promising, it is still too early to propose systems and draw conclusions.

The next steps will be the multiplication of listening points and dissemination of the project to get, as much as possible, to interested communities in order to study and understand the specific needs and approaches.

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